

The use of Code - Switching and Code - Mixing in Kiran Desai's novel *The Inheritance of Loss*

Jayshree Aher

Research Scholar, Dept of English, Sangamner, Nagarpalika College, Sangamner, Dist. Ahmednagar

Corresponding Author – Jayshree Aher

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Abstract:

Nowadays, the use of two or more languages is a typical trend cum necessity of new generation and it is called Bilingualism or multilingualism. Code - Switching and Code- Mixing are an integral part of multilingual speech community. In India the use of Code - Switching in literature started in earliest novels and the novels written during the middle and after independence periods. Authors such as Mulk Raj Anand, in his novels *Coolie* and *Untouchable* used Code - Switching in the earliest period. He used vernacular Hindi, Punjabi languages and English for the purpose of Code - Switching. In postcolonial period Amitov Ghosh, in his novels *The Hungry Tide* and *The Glass Palace* blended English with Bengali, Bhojpuri. Arundhati Roy in his novel *The God of Small Things* used Code Switching immensely. Salman Rushdie, Chetan Bhagat all these writers used Code - Switching in their novels. In India especially in middle Postcolonial era authors often used the technique of Code - Switching and they have preferred the blending between English and regional languages like Hindi, Bengali, Marathi. Kiran Desai has used code - switching and code- mixing immensely in her second novel *The Inheritance of Loss*. Here this study aims at highlighting the linguistic elements in Kiran Desai's novel *The Inheritance of Loss*. Multiculturalism is an important aspect and the theme of this novel. To highlight the aspects of multiculturalism Kiran Desai's has introduced various characters. These characters are presented from different nations with their own customs and with their own languages so its trace is highlighted by these linguistic elements. In her novel *The Inheritance of Loss* Desai has used two codes English and Hindi for her characters. Of course these linguistic elements provide different glamour and beautiful touch to her novel and because of it this novel proves its peculiarity and differentness which adds beauty to this novel. In British literature the way Jane Austen's smooth language and her writing style allures readers, in the same way Kiran Desai has shown her different style and permanently stamped her peculiarity in the literary field.

Keywords: Codes / Code - Switching and Code- Mixing; Glamour; Globalization; Allure; Linguistic Hybridity; Socioeconomic Mobility; Multiculturalism; Authenticating Reality; Cultural Preservation etc.

Introduction:

Kiran desai is the daughter of renowned novelist Anita Desai. Anita Desai has been shortlisted for Booker prize three times for her novels, *Clear Light of Day*, *In Custody*, *Fasting Feasting*. Anita Desai is highly acclaimed Indian Novelist for her contribution to literature. while her daughter Kiran desai is late novelist of the postmodern India. She was born on September 3, 1971, in New Delhi. She grew up in India and

until the age of 15 she lived in India and then moved to England and later the United States. Two novels are to her credit and she has written her third and latest novel recently. Her first novel is *Hullabaloo in the guava Orchard* and her second novel is *The Inheritance of Loss*. Her third novel is *The Loneliness of Sonia and Sunny*. Kiran Desai's novels gain fame and name and spread widely. Her second novel *The Inheritance of Loss* got the booker prize in 2006

and National Book Critics Circle Fiction Award. This novel has touched the problems of identity, multiculturalism etc but it has tackled these issues very smoothly.

Code mixing in the novel *The Inheritance of Loss*:

"Code Mixing is the use of two or more language systems in different contexts". Simply speaking Code Mixing is the insertions of linguistic units like words, phrases or clauses from one language to another in the same speech situation and it occurs in single sentence.

The examples of Code mixing in the novel *The Inheritance of Loss*:

1. " never mind with all this nakhra"
2. Here your sahib will help you."
3. " la! what kind of sahib? " the leader asked the judge.
4. "loudly, can't here you, huzoor. say it louder.
5. "and a pile of mitthai has been spilled.
6. "Thereby angering two snakes mia bibi husband and bibi, who lived in the whole nearby. And did puja.
7. "Respected pitaji, no need to worry". Everything is fine.
8. In Alaska, a desi owned the last general store in the last town before the north pole.
9. And pieces of it in the slipping of the pallu over her head.
10. They'd go running to the bazaar again.
11. They had a self righteousness common to many Indian women of the English speaking upper educated, went out to Mimosa brunches, ate their Dadi's roti with adept fingers, donned a sari.
12. Huge haveli, like a palace.
13. Rice - dal, roti namak, over and over.
14. Calm down bhai.
15. passport photo chahiye? Campa Cola chahiye..
16. What kind of asharam.
17. Now you will have to do the puja.
18. by three police men with guns and lathis.
19. phone la! phone! la mai!

Code Switching in the novel *The Inheritance of Loss*:

According to Diebold, "Code Switching is the successive alternate use of two or more languages within the same discourse"

1. " Ai aaa, ai aaa", he joined his palms together.
2. Go sit in the kithen, bar bar karta rehta hai.
3. The Cook broke into a loud lament: Hamara kya hoga,hai hai, what will become of us"
4. Angrezi khana only, no Indian food, and the owner not from India.
5. dehra dun! devastated, kamal hai, said the Cook.
6. Baap re! I'm never told anything.
7. dhanyawad, shukriya, thank you. extra trip.
8. Angrez ki tarah. like the English
9. the owner was on the speakerphone, "Rajnibhai kem chho?"
10. by the time he had returned home he would have lost his faith in science and begun to howl : "hai hai hamara kya hoga, hai hai hamara kya hoga?"
11. bhai dekho, aisa hai....", he would begin to lecture them.
12. Chalo, Chalo another day, another dollar.
13. no ghas phoos, no twigs and leaves!" said uncle Potty.
14. they call this the first world war, ekdum bekkar.
15. Go will you? bhago, a man said pointing now with his rifle.
16. he sang loudly "O, yeh ladki zarasi deewani lagti hai"

For the technique of code mixing and Code-Switching Desai has used created her own format. For code mixing she has used particular word units. Further while Switching from English language to Hindi

Desai has set her own particular pattern:

1) First Desai has used Marathi exclamation for expression:

e.g. Ai, Aaa!, Baap re!, Kamal hai!, Oof ho!, , Hai- hai!, Chalo, chalo yaar.

2) Further Desai has used typical Indian words:

e.g. Namaste, puja, Nakhara, Sahib, Tamasha, Jawan, Huzoor, Ashram, Gow wallah, Rice, Dal, Roti, Atta, Namak, Bilkul bekar, Haveli, aayiye, baithiye, khayiye.

The use of these particular words is a part of Indian people's life for their today use of communication.

3) Further she has used Indian songs:

e.g. 1. Oyeh ladki zara si deewani lagti hai

2. Mera jota hai Japani

3. Bombai se aaya mera dost

4. Chandani rate, pyaar ki baate

5. Allah hoo, Allah hoo

6.... ke liye jaenge, bhel puri khaenge....kamaenge.

4) Indian relations:

e.g. Kakas-Kakis, Masas-Masis, Phoos-Phuas, Mai, Ammy, Mai, mia bibi.

5) Body pains:

e.g. A thun - thun and Chun - Chun

6) Religious expressions and marching (community) words:

e.g. Wahe guruji ka khalsa, wahe guruji ki fateh, Jai Gorkha.

7) Indian food:

Dal- Roti, Rice, Namak, Pilau, Thunda Khichari, Tikka Masala, Tandoori grill, dal makhani, pappadum, Kheer, mitthai.

8) Indian abuses:

e.g. The machoot sala, uloo ka patha, chaar sau bees, kutti etc.

For this technique of code - Switching and code mixing Kiran desai has used two codes in her novel **The Inheritance of Loss**. These two codes are English and Hindi. Few Punjabi and French words are used by Desai. Further she has used two settings for this novel, India and America. Half of the novel is set in Kalimpong that is the place in India and for the remaining part of the novel she has used American setting. Hindi is the common language in India. Indians are well acknowledged with Hindi so they generally use Hindi for their day today conversation. They can speak and understand Hindi very easily and conveniently though some people are illiterate. In India other languages like Marathi, Gujrathi, Kannad, Tamil, Malayalam etc are also prominent but these are the regional languages. Regional languages are restricted to particular region so these languages are not used widely all over the India. They have limited speakers but in contrast to it Hindi is used throughout the country without any restriction. In the same way in America, people are using English language as their common language and they comprehend it simultaneously with its phonetics and semantics. People can communicate with each other very easily and efficiently through this English language.

These two common languages Hindi of India and English of America reflecting Desai's own attachment with these two nations. Kiran Desai is born in new Delhi, India in september3, 1971. she spent her early years in Chandigarh, Punjab and Mumbai. At the age of 14 she left India, living in England for a year before moving to the United States. Desai's multiple uses of these two languages showing her close bonding and emotional attachment to both the nations and both the languages which are reflected by these

linguistic techniques. Its unique reflection is leading to the problems of multiculturalism and globalization.

Key aspects of Code - Switching and Code-Mixing:

1) **Different Nationality:** the characters in *The Inheritance of Loss* are presented from different nations like India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Czechoslovakia etc so each Character is using their own languages for specific purposes.

2) **Socioeconomic Mobility and Strategy:** many times the characters Switches from English language to their own language or mixes both Hindi and English with each other it may be to show their different social status.

3) **Identity and Resistance:** the use of Hindi or Punjabi, or Nepali words functions as highlighter's cultural identity and resistance especially lower class against marginalization.

4) **Authenticating Reality:** Desai uses the technique of code switching and mixing may be to show her closeness to India and America at the same time. By using this she may wants to reveal her identity and her attachment to both the nations.

5) **Linguistic Hybridity:** Desai often uses inter-sentential Code - Switching by alternating sentences and uses Code- Mixing for highlighting the hybridity of the postcolonial languages.

6) **Cultural Preservation:** though these characters maintain alternative discourses among themselves bypassing the standard language imposed by dominant power structures.

7) **Multiculturalism:** because of globalization and Multiculturalism language gets transferred to different regions e.g. the name of Judge's house is Cho Oyu while the name of Lola and Noni's house is Mon Ami both these are French names used for houses in India. the name of various Cafés in America is also the result of multiculturalism. e.g. Le Colonial, Pinocchio's Italian restaurant.

Conclusion:

The techniques of code switching and code mixing play an important linguistic role in Desai novel *The Inheritance of Loss*. It gives different linguistic touch to her novel which brings East and West elements together. The East and West elements give globalized touch to her novel. The techniques of code switching and code mixing help Desai to put forward the central themes of globalization and multiculturalism. code switching and code mixing is remarkable characteristic of this novel. her purpose behind this code switching and code mixing seems to highlight the feelings and identity of the characters and further by such techniques to form the particular effect on the readers.

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